

FORMS AND METHODS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS ' CREATIVE ABILITIES

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Annotation.The article covers the forms of development of students ' creative abilities. Also stuttered are various special methods aimed at developing creative abilities of students. The article focuses on ensuring the character, interest of developing the creative potential of the student in obtaining a quality education in the cross section of the stages of preschool, general secondary, professional and higher education.

Keywords: creativity, psychological, ability, educator , special methods, exercises, games, practical classes, laboratory work, activities, didactic tools.

The development of students ' abilities occurs in the educational and educational process. One of the main conditions for the development of creative abilities in the group in the institution of higher education is the creation of an environment that contributes to the emergence of new ideas and thoughts. The main thing on the way to creating such an environment is to develop a sense of psychological security in students. Criticizing students and feeling that their suggestions are unacceptable or stupid will stop their creativity.

The opinions they express should be treated with respect. The teacher should encourage students to perform difficult tasks, thereby developing their motivation and perseverance. Also, the environment is of particular importance in the development of students ' creative abilities. The room where children's classes are held should be organized in such a way that it is possible for students to freely

move around the auditorium in accordance with the chosen topic and type of training.

K. E. Siolkovsky remarked, "first I discovered commonly known truths, then I began to discover truths known to some, and finally, I began to discover truths not yet known to anyone". Perhaps this is the way to form creative abilities, the way to develop inventiveness and research talent. The task of the teacher is to help the student in this there are various special methods aimed at developing creative abilities. Methods are tools for the development of creative abilities. There are methods: practical, visual, verbal.

Practical methods include exercises, games, practical classes, laboratory work. Various practical teaching methods are used to instill different skills in the student. Analysis, business Games and situational tasks are the most common. These are not only those that attract the intellectual abilities of a person, but also make them look at the situation from different points of view, different roles

The game method involves the use of various components of the game's activities in combination with other methods. Educational games have a wide range of didactic possibilities. With their help, you can formulate a fairly wide range of skills, skills and professionally significant features of the personality of the future specialist, depending on how the preparation and conduct of the game is organized, what motives are put on its basis by developers and teachers.

Visual methods include observation-drawing, viewing images, viewing Film Tapes, listening to recordings. The method of using pictorial and visual materials in the educational process has a number of advantages: - easy assimilation of new material, as well as deepening, strengthening and clarifying existing ideas; - the ability to change the overall picture, changing the number of sheets; - increasing the content of information by often replacing sheets with pictures.

Also, the advantages of such visual tutorials are the artistry of their image of the object under study, the absence of insignificant details that can distract the

attention of students, the great educational ability achieved by their staticity. The use of these learning tools will help to more effectively assimilate learning materials. The use of the visual method in SPO by teachers helps to overcome stereotypes in education, develop new approaches to professional situations. Only the correct use of visualization will help improve the quality of education and improve the effectiveness of the educational process.

Oral methods: story, conversation, reading, discussion, lecture. When working with students, it is advisable to combine all these methods with each other. Oral methods include large requirements for speech, not only for teachers, but also for students. Teacher speech pedagogical and psychological .

In the process of organizing education aimed at the development of creative abilities, great importance is attached to general didactic principles: scientific, systematic, consistency, availability, clarity, activity, strength, individual approach. One of the basic principles of learning is the principle from simple to complex. This principle consists in the gradual development of creative abilities. According to the researchers, the experience of creative activity V. V. Davydova, V. Zankova, V. V. Kraevsky, [5]. Y. Lerner, [3]M. N. Skatkina, D. B. Elkonina is an independent structural element of educational content.

He assumes: - transfer previously learned knowledge to a new situation,
- independent vision of the problem, alternatives to its solution,
- combining previously studied methods into new ones and others.

Any activity, including creative activity, can be presented in the form of the performance of certain tasks. U. E. UNT defines creative tasks as follows.

Creative tasks differ in the following parameters: - the complexity of problem situations in them, - the complexity of mental operations necessary to solve them;- forms of expression of contradictions (clear, hidden). The game offers many classes on the development of creativity. To do this, you need a new type of games: creative, educational games, combined with all their variety under a

common name, it is no coincidence that they all come from a common idea and have their own creative abilities

1. Each game is a task set.
2. Tasks are given to the student in different forms, thereby introducing him to different ways of transmitting information.
3. Tasks are arranged in order of increasing complexity.
4. Tasks have a very wide range of difficulties. Therefore, games can be of interest for many years.
5. The gradual increase in Task difficulties develop creative abilities;
 - development of abilities should begin as early as possible
 - tasks-steps create conditions before developing abilities;
 - creative games should be diverse in content, as they create an atmosphere of free and cheerful creativity.

Play therapy is the most effective form of working with students, in-Game therapy, based on the use of role-playing as one of the most powerful forms of influencing the development of an individual. The play therapy procedure involves performing specific exercises that involve verbal and non-verbal communication, playing different situations.

During the game, each person begins to better understand their feelings ,develops, communication skills, the ability to make their own decisions, tension and fear from other people disappear, self-esteem increases. The game creates a positive emotional background, in which all mental processes proceed most actively. When a student enters the image, his mind works vividly, emotions increase, he sincerely experiences the events depicted. By creating effective conditions for the development of games, adults are able to develop creative abilities, to open up creative potential

Literature used.

1. Andreeva I. N.The ABC of emotional intelligence.Petersburg.: 2012-288

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2. Wexler.D Brain is 100%. intelligence. Memory.creatine.Intuition: Intensive training for the development of super abilities. Moscow: Eksmo, 2015- 848 page
- 3.Zhuravlev A.L., Sergienko E.A., Vilenskaya G.A. Development of concepts in modern psychology. Moscow: Institute of Psychology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2019-815 page
4. Kraevsky V.V. General fundamentals of pedagogy. 2nd ed. - Moscow:2005-256 page
5. Pryazhnikova E.Y. Psychology of labor. Textbook for academic baccalaureate. Moscow:2016. Publishing house Yurayt obshch. 520 page
6. Elkonin D.B. Child psychology. Publishing house akademiya. M:2007-384-page